

“JSS Mutt Initiative for Universal Health”

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Source: Brochure of The Health Care, JSS Mutt Mysuru

‘Health is Wealth,’ this is a famous adage from time immemorial. Neither India nor the rest of the world can look forward to the life of a man, a prophet, a great saint of the vision, structure and dimension in the centuries to come. Here we have the highest realms of philosophy, religion, Nation, Society, Culture, Welfare of the human mankind¹.

The above statement is brilliantly suitable to His Holiness Shree Jagadguru Dr.Shree Shivarathri Rajendra Swamiji and Jagadguru Shree Shivarathri Deshikendra Swamiji and their contributions, social dedication in the universal service to the mankind, leave alone India, Karnataka and the city of Mysuru.

This kind of self-induced service to mankind could occupy great souls only when they are spiritual and humble to the core².

The lame excuse of lack of funds and such disincentives never deterred the commitment of this great dreamer turned pragmatist. This dreamer and an extraordinary soul with his total dedication have given the countrymen a vision, a dream, and a visionary ideal, to turn dreams into vision, vision into thoughts and thoughts that will transform into a great action³.

1 The Manorama Year Book 2016.

2 JSS Spiritual Mission – 2014.

3 The competition Success year Book 1998.

This great visionary has designed providently for the welfare of the new millennium a great vision of health and one needs to know that good health is the primary need of the next generation. The great saint has charted out a new course for the society in the realms of the service sector for better human development.

JSS mutt is a spiritual center known all over India and has huge popularity amongst the masses. The greatest saints who have represented this mutt over the years have contributed immensely for the spiritual enlightenment of the common masses apart from spreading education and creating a conscious society in Karnataka and other states of India. Thorough JSS Mahavidyapeeta has also rendered yeomen service in the field of health struggling to achieve the universal goal of health for all. Through its universal service JSS MVP has followed a path of devotion to serve the nation and uphold the name of the country at international forums. The great saints of this institute have always held aloft the principle that Work is worship and they are serving the mankind through education and health JSS MVP has, over the years served the masses of Mysuru, Karnataka and also India with the sole aim of free education for all and free health for everyone. Those visionaries who have concern for the common masses and strive for their good health have established hospitals and served the people. JSS is one such great institute. Every citizen of the country needs to know how the JSS MVP has served the common masses in the field of health care contributing towards achieving the goal of good health governance at national and international level through JSS MVP.

The objectives of the Ministry of Health and family welfare, National Health Portal ⁴Are as under

- Improve Health Literacy.
- Improve Access to Health Services.
- Decrease the Burden of Disease through public Awareness.

The National Health Portal is a Gate way to Authentic Health Information

- Hospital Near you.
- Ambulance Services.
- Blood Banks
- Emergency Helpline
- Healthy living

The above-said objects have been mentioned in the J.S.S. MVP organization's portals in Mysuru, Karnataka State⁵.

Health is considered as a state of complete physical, mental spiritual and social well-being. The JSS MVP has made significant strides through various programs in its service to the countrymen. Health is one of the Vital parameters of a country's development, though Health may not be considered as a Fundamental Right. However, a liberal interpretation of article 21 of the Constitution of India will mean so. One may attempt to cover Right to Health as an integral part of Article 21 that guarantees Right to life and personal liberty⁶. There are various provisions under the Constitution of India which deal with the health of the public at large (Dr. S. Venkatesh, From MDG Desk)⁷.

To ensure this right to its people. The technical leadership has to be strong enough to meet the challenges of providing universal health care. Improving life and ensuring the health and well-being of its people throughout the Nation, especially Karnataka state and Mysuru.

4 Director General of Health Services of India.

5 The Health Care, JSS Mutt Mysuru.

6 Committed to uphold the value of human life – Brochure.

7 Dr. Vishwanatha, Kayakaparikalpane, University of Mysore.

JSS Hospital, run under the aegis of JSS Medical Service Trust, JSS MVP offers several healthcare programs and facilities to the needy and poor either FREE or at a subsidized cost. Here is a list of options available to donors to espouse the cause of JSS Medical Services Trust.

Donate/Contribute

You can donate or contribute to JSS Hospital through cash, check, demand draft, payroll reduction and gifts of property. Checks or DD should be drawn in favor of JSS Medical Service Trust, payable at Mysore.

Poor Patient's Fund

Majority of patients coming for treatment to JSS hospital are poor, hailing from surrounding villages. The hospital has created a "Poor Patient's Fund" to help poor patients. Donations are collected from the staff of JSS hospital, allied institutions, general public and philanthropists. The fund is used to meet the treatment expenses of poor patients. This apart, the hospital also offers discounts/concessions in the total treatment charges to deserving patients.

Sponsor a Health Camp

JSS Hospital periodically conducts health camps in rural areas. These health camps usually offer treatments free or at a subsidized cost. The objective of these health camps is to reach the unreached and create health awareness among the people. You may contribute to this cause by sponsoring (full or part) a health camp. Details about health programs organized by the hospital and cost involved can be obtained by corresponding with us.

Sponsor an Operation

A large majority of people in our country do not have access to healthcare and cannot afford emergency and high-end healthcare services. Medical exigencies throw finances of several low-income families out of gear. Our 'Sponsor an Operation' program is designed to help poor people in need of operation but do not have the backing of health insurance. If you choose to enter into this program and indicate the amount you are willing to keep aside for 'sponsor an operation' programme, you will be intimated during a medical emergency or need to 'sponsor an operation.'

The new JSS Hospital Facility with 1,800 beds under One Roof is One-of India's Biggest Hospitals

Well-Equipped to Provide Advanced Healthcare in Every Discipline

The new JSS Hospital facility with 1,800 beds under one roof is one of India's biggest hospitals. It also has one of the biggest critical and emergency care facilities with 260 beds. The motto of the hospital is to uphold the value of human life and provide advanced and affordable healthcare to all sections of society.

The hospital has state-of-the-art infrastructure and the most advanced equipment. It is a non-profit hospital and is dedicated to serving the poor and downtrodden with affordable and quality healthcare. The new facility is located in an area of 12.5 acres and has a built-up space of 12.5 lakh sq ft. The hospital provides service in 37 specialties/super specialties and has 55 special clinics. It plans to cater to the healthcare needs of more than 16,000 outpatients in addition to the existing number of 18,000 and 3,500 inpatients every month.

The Higher Education Ranking List of Times “Higher Education World University Ranking has announced a list on 28-09-2018 and JSS University has got the 3rd Place”⁸.

The mutt is providing a visionary service to the common masses and it is serving the masses irrespective of caste and creed. By peoples’ mandate, JSS mutt has contributed towards the good Health of the society, State and the nation as well, in search of Universal truth.

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⁸ World University Ranking Sept. 28, 2018.